

**Accessible, reliable, and affordable solar irrigation for
Europe and beyond**

Deliverable 4.5 Policy SI-action

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Acronyms

CAP	Common Agrarian Policy
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EAFRD	European Agriculture Fund for Rural Development
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EU	European Union
FI	Financial Instrument
kW	Kilowatt
kWp	Kilowatt peak
MA	Managing Authority
MW	Megawatt
PA	Public Authority
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
PVIS	Photovoltaic Irrigation System
RDP	Rural Development Programme
SI	Solar Irrigation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

SolaQua in a nutshell

SolaQua's overall objective is to increase the share of **renewable energy (RE)** consumption in Europe by facilitating the market uptake of **solar irrigation (SI)** in the farming sector. SI is based on a combination of **photovoltaic (PV)** technology, hydraulic engineering, and high-efficiency water management techniques to optimize irrigated farming.

The consortium of SolaQua, which represents more than 70% of European irrigators, is aware of the potential of SI to decisively improve the sustainability of farming and rural communities in Europe. Nevertheless, to fulfil this potential, it is necessary to overcome the existing barriers to the market uptake of SI. To do this, SolaQua will accelerate the clean energy transition in European agriculture by facilitating the development of a well-functioning market for SI. This will be done by producing and exploiting a set of **7 Key Enabling Materials and Tools (KEMT)** and by creating awareness, skills, action, engagement, and commitment (ASAEC) opportunities among more than 150,000 farmers, 70 local SMEs, and 40 Public Administrations in Europe and beyond.

The execution of SolaQua will result not only in a reduction of the cost of SI for farmers but also in the availability of effective standards for consumers and environmental protection, more efficient policies and supporting schemes, and new business opportunities for SMEs. Furthermore, to exploit the project's results and to trigger the SI market, SolaQua will facilitate a joint promotion of more than 100 MW of reliable and affordable SI led by the end-users themselves: the farmers.

To achieve the overall objective of increasing the share of RE in the European farming sector by facilitating SI market uptake, SolaQua has established the following 5 specific objectives:

- 1. Produce and disseminate a set of 7 KEMT**, designed to solve technical, economic, and legal issues which are acting as barriers for the market uptake of SI.
- 2. Produce awareness and skills of SI among the target groups in six countries** (France, Italy, Spain, Romania, Portugal, and Morocco). At least 150,000 potential end-users will be reached, 70 SMEs will be trained, and 38 Public Authorities will be able to produce more informed policies and supporting schemes.
- 3. Trigger the European SI market by facilitating a joint promotion of at least 100 MW of SI**, exploiting SolaQua's KEMT and led by the target audiences engaged in SI because of the project's dissemination and communication actions.
- 4. Increase the effectiveness of public supporting schemes for on-farm investments for the promotion of SI**: SolaQua will produce a new European Agrarian Fund for Rural Development (EAFDR) financial instrument that will be implemented in 3 European regions and will support more than 40 MW of new SI capacity.
- 5. Facilitate market uptake of reliable and affordable SI in markets outside the EU** that will result not only in increased cooperation but also in business opportunities for European SME's and investors.

2. Purpose and scope

This report D4.5 (Policy SI-action) summarises the plans of Aragon (Spain), Valencia (Spain) and Calarasi (Romania) to facilitate the introduction of photovoltaic irrigation systems (PVI) and the development of an efficient market for such technology through the implementation of specific actions.

3. Methodology

This document has been produced on the basis of deliverables 2.12 "[Legal Analyses and Best Practices](#)", where the existing legislation and practices in the different Mediterranean countries were analysed, and 2.13 "[EAFRD Financial Instrument for Rural Development](#)" which includes the actions to be carried out by the regional/national authorities to implement the Financial Instrument (FI) in the Rural Development Programmes. The authorities of the concerned regions have identified the **main obstacles of their legislation** and they have picked some **recommendations to tackle them**.

It is divided into three points, one for each regional authority (Aragon, Valencia, and Romania). Each of them follows a similar structure, a first part with a list of identified obstacles and a table with recommendations that should be followed and possible actions to be implemented. The results of the aforementioned activities are summarized in the sections to follow.

4. Aragon

A- Main obstacles identified.

The main regulations and laws affecting the installation and operation of PVI in the region of Aragon are:

- Royal Decree 244/2019, of 5 April, which regulates the administrative, technical, and economic conditions for the self-consumption of electricity.
- Royal Decree-Law 23/2020, of 23 June, approving measures in the field of energy and other areas for economic reactivation.
- Royal Decree 960/2020, of 3 November, which regulates the economic regime of renewable energies for electricity production facilities.
- Law 21/2013, of 9 December, on environmental assessment and its amendment by Law 9/2018, of 5 December.
- Law 11/2014, of 4 December, on Environmental Prevention and Protection of Aragon.
- Royal Legislative Decree 1/2001, of 20 July, approving the revised text of the Water Law.

After the revision of the regulations and laws and with the aim of facilitating the uptake of solar energy consumption in the agricultural sector, several obstacles are identified.

<p style="text-align: center;">FOR SELF- CONSUMPTION</p>	<p>Self-consumption, grid-connected. There are two relevant system configurations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. without commercializing electricity surpluses 2. commercializing electricity surpluses (most common in irrigation communities (IC)) <p>If the system is type 2, there are two different cases:</p> <p>Case I. PV systems smaller than 100 kWp are well suited as they can inject surpluses in the electrical grid but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It takes at least three months to obtain the permit. • The 100 kWp threshold is too low for the needs of a typical IC, so it should be consequently increased to at least 1 MWp. • Surpluses are paid in discounts (not in kWh) over a specific period which means that the invoice of the period must be sufficiently high to absorb the discount. <p>Case II. Regulation is less suited for PVIS larger than 100 kWp are because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The IC must be incorporated as an energy producer enterprise on the business register. • They must pay VAT. • The distribution system operator decides where you can connect the PVI to the grid. Most of the times no interconnection point is available. • In practical terms the interconnection of PVIs larger than 100 kWp is not possible, so ICs have undersized PVIS or simply do not take surpluses into account when building a PVIS
<p style="text-align: center;">FOR ENERGY COMMUNITIES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They must be in 500 m radio of the PV generator. • The same cadastral reference number in land registry. • They must take and inject electricity in the same administrative plot (this is not possible for ICs), which means that the production and consumption needs to take place within a independent farm (ICs are communal entities)
<p style="text-align: center;">FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PERMISSIONS</p>	<p>In Aragón, 30% of the territory is Natura2000, so it is likely that a PVI project requires an ordinary environmental assessment (instead of a simplified one), which can take more than a year to be completed. Simplified environmental assessment is quicker than the ordinary, but not much.</p>

Finally, apart from the environmental assessment, the Article 42 of Law 11/2014, of 4 December (transposition of article 6 Habitats Directive) requires special permission if the installation is located within Natura2000 or sensitive areas. In Aragón, there are plenty of sensitive areas (river crab, bearded vulture, Bonelli's eagle or lesser kestrel, inter alia), so if a PVIS is built in a sensitive area, (even if it is only two solar panels), permission is also required, taking 3-6 months to be completed.

Building a PVIS in the hydraulic public domain (e.g., beside a river or a river nearby), also requires environmental permissions. In these areas, there are lots of suitable spots for PVIS (pumping from the river).

Furthermore, some problems have been identified related to the use of Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs):

- If the market price of electricity remains so high potential PPA promoters can be more interested in selling the energy to the grid than to irrigators at a fixed price contract.
- If Potential PPA offtakes expect a fall in the prices, they may lack incentives to sign a fixed price contract as the energy price could be lower in the future.

B- Recommendations and main actions to tackle the obstacles.

This section groups the main recommendations and actions that should be followed by the Government of Aragón to tackle the aforementioned obstacles.

Recommendation	Main actions
<p>Regulation governing the photovoltaic sector - PVIS Market: Introduce simplified administrative procedures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall, administrative procedures should be simpler or, at least, quicker. • The threshold of the size of the PVIs for simplified commercialization of surpluses should be raised to 1MWp (best suited for irrigation communities and make it easier for systems in the range of 1-2 MWp). • The price of the kWh from surpluses should be higher or, at least, closer to market levels. The clearance should be done every year, although it would be better to be settled in energy instead of in cash (net metering). • Promote and facilitate the operation of energy communities (specially for Irrigation communities)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate environmental permissions, at least Art. 42 of Law 11/2014, of 4 December (transposition of article 6 Habitats Directive)
<p>Legislation applying for electrical grid access and connections procedures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Current requirements are outdated, it should be completely changed. Guarantee the access of any IC to the electrical grid, at least up to a certain MW amount or depending on the surface or the PVI (solar panels surface) Authorization from electricity producers or distributors (Endesa, Iberdrola, or any other) should be automatic until 2 MWp. Easier and quicker permissions
<p>Ensuring the quality of PVIS projects and the availability of key competences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any subsidy to PVIS projects should be conditional to the present sufficient quality.
<p>Increase the attractiveness of PVIS projects to a wide range of stakeholders</p>	<p>a) Improve the expected return for investors of PVIS projects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> By introducing direct subsidies and grants for PVIS projects but also by using other type of measures designed to support the financial suitability of the projects, such as dedicated credit facilities. <p>b) Facilitate local stakeholders to benefit from PVIS deployment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> By organizing training and dissemination activities at local level to increase the know-how on PVIS and to ensure sufficient project development skills among professionals Dissemination of the supporting instruments and PPA possibilities in the irrigation communities, through different EAFRD lines, especially if a dedicated financial instrument (FI) is finally approved in the PEPAC. In case of this approval, FI and PPA could be introduced in the different PEPAC tools, such as the PEPAC Communication Plan, Training and Knowledge transfer. Setting up meetings with the following key territorial actors and stakeholders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oficina del regante de Aragón Irrigation communities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Governmental departments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dirección General de Industria y Pymes del Departamento de Industria. • Dirección General de Ordenación del Territorio del Departamento de Vertebración del territorio, movilidad y vivienda. • Dirección General de Urbanismo del Departamento de Vertebración del territorio, movilidad y Vivienda.
<p>Allow access to affordable, long-term finance by using tailored EAFRD financial instruments to support the introduction of high quality PVIS.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Developing a Financial Instrument and introducing facilities in the PEPAC through EAFRD. The process to be followed will be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the need of finance for investments in photovoltaic energy generation for irrigation. • Include a FI for PVIS in the strategic plan (National Strategic Plan / Rural Development Plan). • Determine the type of instrument: Centralised, European Investment Bank, from the Autonomous Community. • Produce an ex-ante evaluation - the Autonomous Regions that were already using FIs in the previous period or that want to use them in the future must consider integrating the PVIS FI within the Ministry's working group. • Consider including Aragón's PVIS FI in the Spanish Centralised financial instrument - Spanish government leads it, intermediates with the EC (DG AGRI) and with the financial institutions. • The Spanish government carry out negotiations with financial institutions to assess their interest in managing this financial instrument. • The entities sign an agreement with the Ministry and the Autonomous Regions. • The Autonomous Regions develop regulatory bases for the instrument and a call for applications to be submitted by PVI promoters.

5. Comunitat Valenciana

A- Main obstacles identified.

The Government of the Comunitat Valenciana has approved two Decree-Laws relevant to the implementation of the SolAqua project, as they favour the installation of photovoltaic power plants. This legislation is part of the response of the public authorities to the international pandemic caused by Covid-19 and to the humanitarian and energy crisis caused by the Russian invasion of Ukraine, both due to their high economic impact.

- **Decree-Law 14/2020, of 7 August, of the Council, on measures to accelerate the implementation of facilities for the use of renewable energies due to the climate emergency and the need for urgent economic recovery**, places the renewable energy sector at the centre of its regulation, and more specifically that of electricity production facilities based on the conversion of these energies into electricity, as one of the fundamental axes of this change of model.

The increased use of energy from renewable sources also plays a key role in promoting security of energy supply, sustainable energy supply at more affordable prices and innovation, as well as providing environmental and social benefits and numerous opportunities for employment and regional development, especially in rural and isolated areas, in regions or territories with low population density or partially affected by deindustrialisation.

As a particularly relevant aspect, this Decree-Law declares photovoltaic and wind energy production facilities to be "investments of strategic interest for the Valencian Community", as these are the two most mature renewable technologies at present, which complement each other adequately to cover demand within intermittent renewable energies and which are based on inexhaustible and free natural resources, and which are almost exclusively backed by both public energy planners and economic operators in the sector, as they account for almost all the projects underway, including the project in question.

This declaration means benefits for this type of installations due to the priority in administrative procedures in the Valencia Region for their construction and start-up, all based on the objectives and deadlines for achieving them imposed by various energy and climate strategies and plans approved, or in very advanced stages of processing, by the various Community, national and regional authorities.

Therefore, the measures contained in this Decree-Law are designed to promote a clean, fair and economically competitive energy transition that facilitates the economic recovery of the Valencian Community and serves as an opportunity to accelerate the energy transition so that investments in renewables, with the economic activity and employment that will be associated with them, act as a lever for the recovery of the Valencian economy.

- **Decree Law 1/2022, of 22 April, of the Council**, on urgent measures in response to the energy and economic emergency caused in the Valencian Community by the war in Ukraine, updates some of the previous wording of the Decree Law 14/2020 described above.

Firstly, it promotes regulatory changes based on the basic principle of eliminating bureaucratic obstacles and converting the Administration into an accelerator of the energy transition aimed at favouring the installation of renewable energies in the Valencian territory with greater facilities, without prejudice to the specific regulations for installations in which authorisation corresponds to the Generalitat. The Valencia region currently produces 66% of all the energy it consumes. The Council aims is to move towards energy self-sufficiency in the region. The 315 renewable energy projects currently being processed (at a regional and national level) would represent an additional installed capacity of around 10,000 MW, including solar and wind energy, which would make it possible to overcome the region's current dependence on foreign energy sources.

Secondly, this decree law promotes other legal modifications to facilitate new private investment projects that stimulate the Valencian economy and employment. Among them, and in particular, all those investments that can benefit from the extraordinary financing foreseen in the European Union's recovery instrument. Considering the depth and ramifications of the crisis that this war led to, the Valencian institutions must tackle all the necessary reforms to protect the recovery that had already been consolidated.

This is, in short, an initial emergency regulation, without prejudice to the necessary subsequent reflection that will make possible to identify other needs for modification in order to achieve the ambitious goal of this modification of regulations: to tend, over the next five years, towards the energy sovereignty of the Valencian Community.

The financial instrument arising from the SolAqua project aims to promote the financing of projects to modify the irrigation system of Valencian crops, so that they can be irrigated with photovoltaic energy. **This instrument is being studied centrally through a nationwide working group, in which the Generalitat is in negotiations to become a member.**

Thus, in order for the Financial Instrument to be put in place, the regions that form part of the project must participate with a contribution of funds from their budget within the Strategic Plan of the CAP and in the case of the Generalitat Valenciana it is the Agricultural Development and Guarantee Agency that manages the European Union's EAFRD funds.

At present, these funds (estimated in 4.8 million euros of EAFRD funds for "irrigation and agricultural infrastructures") are distributed among different Directorates. This amount is in addition to the compulsory regional and state contribution of a further 3.2 million euros and an additional, voluntary regional contribution of 12 million euros, making a total of 20 million euros for this line of aid.

Within the framework of the Generalitat's Strategic Plan, which has already been approved, it is planned to make the necessary modifications to be able to allocate approximately 4 million euros to the project, without expressing a binding commitment.

Furthermore, the Generalitat will not only take the necessary actions to include the Financial Instrument in question, but also carry out the studies required for the ex-ante evaluation conducted at the state level.

B- Recommendations and main actions to tackle the obstacles.

Recommendation	Main actions	
	WHAT	HOW
<p>Facilitate local stakeholders to benefit from the deployment of PV systems by –</p> <p>Introducing specific support actions targeted at local SMEs that can act as PV project developers or suppliers. –</p> <p>Organising training activities at local level to introduce PV knowledge and project development skills among professionals.</p>	<p>A conference to analyse the possibilities of using the Centralised Management Financial Instrument that has been in operation in Spain since 2014-2020 for some of the interventions of the CAP SP.</p>	<p>Disseminating the financial instruments that are being implemented in the field of the CAP through the experience of Castilla León.</p>
	<p>A presentation on the SolAqua project for irrigation communities and local installers.</p>	<p>Participating in the assemblies of Irrigation Communities to make the project known to potential stakeholders</p>
	<p>Bilateral meetings with the departments of the GVA related to the management of EAFRD funds.</p>	<p>Attending meetings with the Autonomous Secretariat for Agriculture, the Valencian Agricultural Development and Guarantee Agency (AVFGA) and the Directorate General for Agriculture.</p>
	<p>To report local and regional authorities, irrigation communities, farmers, and financial institutions.</p>	<p>Disseminating the objectives of the project and the financing models, as well as the fixed price contracts and their characteristics, so that local entities, irrigation communities and farmers themselves can spread the word about the project or new interested parties.</p>
	<p>Attending other workshops and events (within the project) in collaboration with the CPMR</p>	<p>Assisting in the organisation of events by the CPMR to present the results of the SolAqua project. Organisation of a conference to present the project to different public administrations managing EU funds.</p>
<p>Increase citizen support for PVIS projects by promoting the use of collective</p>	<p>To implement the Financial Instrument currently under development, the Generalitat Valenciana has an important role to play in the dissemination of PPA contract models to raise awareness of their existence and use.</p>	

<p>forms of ownership of PVIS projects (such as SPVs) by giving priority to local investors and community schemes.</p>	<p>To this end, the terms, and conditions of the calls for applications for access to guarantees by investors must establish the standardised contract model that acts as a safeguard for the rights of the consumer (the irrigator) and provides legal certainty. Furthermore, this standard contract is intended to reduce costs and time, since it will define the quality requirements of the system and the actions to be taken in the event of non-compliance, as well as the immovable bases on which to negotiate each specific contract.</p> <p>Within the framework of these proposals, it is also intended to promote access to these contracts and, consequently, to the SolaQua project guarantees for collective property communities that can commercialise energy surpluses and that are already dedicated to the autonomous production of 100% renewable energy, such as Sapiens Energía or Som energia, for example.</p>
<p>Supporting risk assessment of PVIS - Supporting banks and development agencies to acquire knowledge and skills in PVIS project assessment and modelling</p>	<p>Related to the previous point, as part of the preparation and dissemination of the PPA contracts, the entities providing guarantees or loans to the PVI promoters must be aware of all the risks involved in the implementation of solar panels to produce photovoltaic irrigation.</p> <p>Therefore, to ensure sufficient awareness among these entities, the Generalitat will also include them among the parties invited to the conferences to be held to publicise the SolaQua project, as well as the financial instrument and the model contracts.</p>
<p>Facilitating local stakeholders to benefit from the deployment of the PVI</p>	<p>Currently, the supporting tools available in Valencia for projects aimed to upgrade the irrigation systems of the irrigation communities are subsidies to investment. In this case, following the call for applications for subsidies, beneficiaries are required to submit a project in order to be reviewed by the project supervision service of the Regional Ministry of Agriculture. Given the similarity of the object of the projects, it would be recommended that this same service should supervise the technical quality of the projects and the suitability of the PPA contracts using the materials produced by the SolaQua project. This can be provided either as technical assistance aimed to the promoters of the project or/and to the financial entities acting as financial intermediaries and loan providers.</p>

6. Calarasi

The Rural Development Programme (RDP) in Romania is financed by EAFRD and national contributions. This implies that, to implement the recommendations of the SolaQua project, the Calarasi County Council must go through the national level administration responsible for the RDP.

The 2014-2020 RDP for Romania focused on 3 main priority axes: promoting competitiveness and restructuring the agricultural sector; environmental protection & climate change; and stimulating economic development, job creation and a better quality of life in Romanian villages.

Under the second axis “environmental protection & climate change”, it puts particular emphasis on resource efficiency for agriculture, which includes modernisation of existing irrigation infrastructure, targeting nearly 400,000 hectares of agricultural land on which the use of water could be more efficient and adapted to increased water scarcity. This would be complemented by training and advisory actions to help farmers adapt farming practices to increase their efficiency of water use¹.

A- Main obstacles identified.

Taking into account deliverable D2.12 Legal analysis and best practice, which was carried out in the framework of the project, the main regulations and laws affecting the use of solar energy in the region of Calarasi are:

- Law no. 220/2008 for the promotion of energy production from renewable energy sources.
- The Electricity and Natural Gas Law no. 123/2012 (“Energy Law”), amended on May 19, 2020, by Government Emergency Ordinance (GEO) no. 74/2020 to expand the possibility to enter into power purchase agreements and on December 28, 2021, with the main purpose of transposing the provisions of Directive (EU) 2019/944 concerning common rules for the internal market in electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU.
- Law no. 220/2008 for the promotion of energy production from renewable energy sources, regulating self-consumption.
- Law no. 220/2008 regulates the establishment of the system for promoting the production of energy from renewable energy sources with subsequent modifications and completions.
- Two orders regulate the connection to the electricity grid: The Order of National Authority for Energy Regulation no. 228 from December 28, 2018 and the Order no. 15 of National Authority for Energy Regulation from 10.03.2021 for the approval of the Procedure regarding the connection to the electricity networks of public interest of the consumption and production places belonging to the prosumers who have installations for the production of electricity from renewable sources with the installed power of at most 100 kW per consumption place.

¹ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-11/rdp-factsheet-romania_en.pdf

- Law no. 138/2004 for Land improvement, regarding the ownership and management of irrigation infrastructures.

At the end of 2022 it was also issued the Emergency Ordinance no. 163/2022 for the completion of the legal framework for the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (Law no. 220/2008), as well as for the modification and completion of some normative acts.

B- Recommendations and main actions to tackle the obstacles.

Despite all these limitations, a number of recommendations have been chosen as they are suited to be adopted by the national authority dealing with the RDP.

Recommendation	Main actions
<p>Regulation governing the photovoltaic sector - PVIS</p> <p>Market: Introduce simplified administrative procedures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential investors who may even be members of Irrigators associations need minimum legislative facilities regarding obtaining the town planning certificate based on plot plan, property title in the extra-urban area and without restrictions on the creditworthiness class. • There are lands near the irrigation systems filled with concrete and rubble from former constructions and listed as land with high creditworthiness. If such facilities will be created, for obtaining the town planning certificate near the pump stations, the irrigation activity will be profitable, the production of green energy will increase, the environment will be protected by reducing carbon emissions and substantially reducing the costs borne by the farmer per ton / grain. • Since the energy sector is strategic and of national interest, existing the opportunity to implement investments financed from the RRRP and from the Fund for modernization, it is required that the authorities with competences in issuing authorizations and approvals to treat with priority all these investments
<p>Allow access to affordable, long-term finance. !</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By creating facilities for non-reimbursable financing of solar energy systems, multiple benefits (economic, social, environmental) would be obtained for agricultural producers and all other stakeholders involved. • The modernization of irrigation systems is ensured with funds from National Agency for Land Improvements, submeasure 4.3, 100% non-refundable co-financing, 1,000,000 €/ association. However, photovoltaic irrigation systems are not yet included. <p>Also, the Recovery and Resilience Plan for Romania (RRPR) offered non-refundable financing for the installation of over 600 MW of</p>

	<p>renewable energy, through the C6 – Energy component of the RRRP, one of the most expected and requested support measures last year.</p>
<p>Facilitate and reduce administrative procedures for PVIS developments and implementations. !</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current legislation only refers to photovoltaic installations in general, not to photovoltaic irrigation systems. • The photovoltaic sector must be regulated by laws that cover all the PV modalities and applications, among them, grid-connected and stand-alone photovoltaic installations. • Laws must ensure that simplified and less burdensome authorisation procedures, including a simple-notification procedure, are established for PV applications. • Administrative procedures to obtain permits and authorizations must be simple and efficient ensuring short time-limits for decisions. • Administrative procedures to obtain permits and authorizations must be simple and efficient ensuring short time-limits for decisions.
<p>Facilitate local stakeholders to benefit from the deployment of PV systems by –</p> <p>Introducing specific support actions targeted at local SMEs–</p> <p>Organising training activities at local level to introduce PV knowledge.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To facilitate introduction of high-quality photovoltaic systems we plan to organize meetings with the representatives of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and the National Agency for Land Improvement (expected to take place in May 2023) • The central and local public administration authorities with responsibilities in the field of promoting energy from renewable sources organize appropriate information programs regarding support measures, which they make available to all relevant factors, as well as to consumers, including vulnerable consumers with low incomes, prosumers of energy from renewable sources, communities of energy from renewable sources, builders, installers, architects, suppliers of equipment and systems of heating, cooling and electricity, as well as suppliers of vehicles compatible with the use of energy from renewable sources and intelligent transport systems.

7. Conclusions and limitations

This deliverable has been elaborated with the support of the government of Aragon, the Comunitat Valenciana and Calarasi, who have provided information from their regions as well as the Polytechnic University of Madrid. It is a document that gathers the main obstacles and recommendations that should be followed to improve the market uptake of photovoltaic irrigation systems (PVI) and to implement the Financial Instrument in their Rural Development Programmes.

The plans of each region to facilitate the introduction of PVI and the development of an efficient market for such technology through the implementation of specific actions is in a different state; while Aragon has already dedicated EAFRD budgetary allocation to it, the Comunitat Valenciana is still in the process of raising awareness of the instrument with the concerned departments in charge of managing the RDPs and EAFRD funds and assessing the possibility of implementing it. In Calarasi, the management of the RDPs is at national level so the recommendations to be followed must be passed to the national authorities for their evaluation and eventual implementation.